

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Impact of low-input agriculture (low fertiliser/pesticide use) via Micro-Econometric Multi-Crop Cost Allocation models *Discussion paper*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Micro-econometric multi-crop (MEMC) models are commonly used in Europe with farm-level panel data but face several empirical challenges, including lacking cost accounting data (which is the case for FADN data), frequent null crop acreages and unobserved heterogeneity across farm(er)s. To overcome these limitations, we propose a new structural model, the Endogenous Regime Switching Micro-Econometric Multi-Crop Model with Cost Input Allocation (MEMC-CA) and assess its empirical performances based on French farm dataset.

This paper presents the MEMC-CA model, which is used to analyze farmers' decisions regarding crop acreages choice, yield levels and variable input uses (pesticides and fertilizers). The model is based on a profit maximization framework at the farm level.

Along the lines of Carpentier and Letort (2012, 2014), the basic modelling framework model integrates three interrelated components: (i) a system of crop acreage choice equations based on an acreage management cost function, (ii) a system of crop yield supply equations, and (iii) a system of variable input demand allocation equations. Crop yield supply and variable input demand equations are derived from quadratic yield functions. Acreage choice equations are derived from a quadratic acreage management cost function, as in Positive Mathematical Programming (PMP) models based on the so-called "PMP term".

Two options are available for dealing with the lack of cost accounting data. The first option involves two steps. First, agrochemicals costs are allocated to the crops of the farms using the (CA, for cost allocation) approach proposed by Koutchadé et al (2024). This two-step modelling framework is called the CA+MEMC model for simplicity. Second, the estimated crop-specific agrochemicals are added to the initial dataset for estimating the MEMC model. The second option consists of replacing the agrochemicals demand equation system of the MEMC model by the variable input allocation equations considered in the CA approach of Koutchadé et al (2024). The resulting model, the MEMC-CA model, is estimated in one step, based on an approach similar to the one employed for estimating the MEMC model.

The empirical application employs an unbalanced panel comprising 1,083 arable farms in northeastern France, observed from 2007 to 2014. The estimation results indicate that the MEMC model provides a good fit for the observed data and captures key features of farmers' production behavior. Model validation shows that the CA+MEMC and MEMC-CA specifications perform well in predicting crop choice and production regimes, particularly in reproducing zero acreage outcomes, as well as (expected) yield levels. However, validation results tend to show that these specifications perform poorly regarding allocation of variable input to crops. More precisely, the quality estimated crop-specific allocation is not sufficient for the calibrated simulation models to provide reliable results for policy directly targeting uses of variable inputs, such as pesticide and/or fertilizer taxes. Yet, the calibrated simulation models can provide reliable results for policies targeting acreage choices, such as area-based coupled payments.

Keywords: null crop acreages, input cost allocation, heterogeneity, crop production decisions, ERS-MEMC models, random parameter models, SAEM algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION

Agri-environmental policies increasingly aim to regulate the use of variable agricultural inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides. Evaluating the impact of these policies requires models that capture how farmers decide on crops, acreage, and variable inputs, considering the interdependence of these decisions and land as quasi-fixed input. Micro-econometric multi-crop (MEMC) models are commonly used in Europe with farm-level panel data but face several empirical challenges, including lacking cost accounting data (as in the case of Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN)), frequent null crop acreages and unobserved heterogeneity across farm(er)s.

Existing MEMC models (Just *et al.*, 1983; Chambers and Just, 1989; Lence and Miller, 1998; Letort and Carpentier, 2010; Koutchade *et al.*, 2018, 2021) typically address some, but not all, of these challenges simultaneously. Approaches that explicitly account for zero acreage often rely on discrete-continuous frameworks or regime-switching structures, which can become computationally demanding in multi-crop settings. Models incorporating random parameters capture heterogeneity but are difficult to estimate in high-dimensional environments. Moreover, the lack of crop-level input data complicates the identification of input demand systems. As a result, the joint modeling of crop choice, acreage choice, variable input use, and yields in a unified and tractable framework remains an open empirical challenge.

This paper develops a structural modeling approach designed to address these issues jointly. We propose an Endogenous Regime Switching Micro-Econometric Multi-Crop model with Cost input Allocation (MEMC-CA). The model assumes that farmers maximize farm-level profit with a quadratic acreage cost structure, allowing acreage choices to be derived from Karush–Kuhn–Tucker optimality conditions. This formulation consistently accommodates zero crop acreages and allows regime structures (i.e., crop sets) to differ across farms and regions. The acreage choice and crop choice components are coupled with crop-level yield supply equations derived from crop-level profit maximization with normalized quadratic production functions. Instead of specifying crop-specific

variable input demand equations, the model introduces variable input allocation equations, enabling the use of farm-level input data when crop-level observations are unavailable.

Relative to the closest contribution in the literature (Koutchadé et al., 2021), our approach offers three main advances. First, we replace the nested logit acreage cost specification with a quadratic acreage cost function, which permits greater flexibility and the consideration of a larger number of production regimes. Second, by modeling input allocation rather than input demand, the framework overcomes the frequent absence of crop-specific input data while accommodating multiple variable inputs. Third, the model maintains a direct structural link with Positive Mathematical Programming (PMP), since the estimated parameters can be used for farm-level calibration and policy simulation. Unlike Koutchadé et al. (2021), however, we do not introduce regime-specific costs.

To account for unobserved heterogeneity, the model incorporates random farm-specific parameters in both acreage, yield and variable input components. We distinguish between persistent heterogeneity across farms and stochastic production shocks affecting specific crops and periods. To estimate this high-dimensional random-parameter regime-switching model, we implement a Stochastic Approximation Expectation-Maximization (SAEM) algorithm, which provides a computationally efficient alternative to Simulated Maximum Likelihood (SML) in settings involving complex likelihood functions and multivariate probability density function integrals.

We apply the proposed framework to panel data on French arable crop producers. The dataset resembles FADN data but also contains crop-level information on fertilizer and pesticide uses, which allows us to evaluate model performance under alternative information structures. We compare the estimates of MEMC-CA model with (a) the estimates of a model that directly leverages the crop-level input uses, the MEMC model, and (b) the estimates of the MEMC-CA model based on a two-step procedure, the CA+MEMC estimates. Following estimation, we conduct farm-level statistical calibration and policy simulations to assess model fit and the implications of alternative modeling choices. The estimation results indicate that the MEMC model provides a good fit for the observed

data and captures key features of farmers' production behavior. Most parameters, including the means and standard deviations of the random coefficients, are precisely estimated, highlighting the importance of unobserved heterogeneity across farms. A key finding is that acreage allocation and variable input use are jointly determined with strong complementarities across inputs. Consequently, policies targeting a single margin, such as taxes on pesticides or fertilizers, are likely to generate indirect adjustments in other inputs and crop choices. For example, a pesticide tax could reduce pesticide use, affect fertilizer application, and induce shifts toward less input-intensive crops. Model validation shows that the CA+MEMC and MEMC-CA specifications perform well in predicting crop choice and production regimes, particularly in reproducing zero acreage outcomes, as well as (expected) yield levels. However, validation results tend to show that these specifications perform poorly regarding allocation of variable input to crops. More precisely, the quality estimated crop-specific allocation is not sufficient for the calibrated simulation models to provide reliable results for policy directly targeting uses of variable inputs, such as pesticide and/or fertilizer taxes. Yet, the calibrated simulation models can provide reliable results for policies targeting acreage choices, such as area-based couple payments

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the related literature. Section 3 presents the structural model. Section 4 discusses identification and estimation. Section 5 reports empirical and simulation results. Section 6 concludes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEWS

Accurately modeling multi-crop production decisions remains a central challenge in agricultural economics, particularly when relying on farm-level datasets such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). While these data provide rich information on crop acreages, outputs, and revenues, they also present structural empirical constraints that complicate micro-econometric multi-crop (MEMC) modeling. Three issues are especially salient: the prevalence of zero crop acreages, the

absence of crop-level input data, and substantial unobserved heterogeneity in production conditions.

The existing literature addresses these challenges only partially, leaving important gaps for policy-relevant modeling.

Farmers rarely cultivate the same set of crops each year. Economic incentives, agronomic rotations, and environmental constraints generate frequent corner solutions in acreage decisions. Consequently, farm-level data contain many zero observations for non-produced crops, creating difficulties for standard regression-based approaches.

Multivariate censored regression models, including extensions of the generalized Tobit framework (e.g., Fezzi and Bateman, 2011; Platoni et al., 2012), provide a statistical treatment of zero outcomes. However, these approaches are not fully consistent with microeconomic theory. In particular, they may imply that prices of non-produced crops influence acreage decisions, which contradicts the structure implied by profit maximization under non-negativity constraints.

Endogenous Regime Switching (ERS) models offer a theoretically coherent alternative (Wales and Woodland, 1983; Lee and Pitt, 1986). These models derive both discrete crop selection and continuous acreage allocation from the Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (KKT) conditions of a constrained optimization problem. Within the MEMC framework, Koutchadé et al. (2021) develop an ERS model – hereafter the KCF model – that combines regime choice with regime-specific systems of acreage, yield, and input demand equations. Their approach relies on an implicit entropic acreage cost function that promotes diversification and ensures tractability.

Despite its theoretical appeal, the ERS approach becomes computationally demanding when the number of potential regimes grows large, as is typical with FADN data. To maintain feasibility, Koutchadé et al. (2021) restrict estimation to the most frequently observed regimes. While practical, this regime-pruning strategy effectively limits the support of the choice set and may attenuate the estimated extensive margin response by excluding less common but economically relevant crop combinations.

An alternative avenue, rooted in the Positive Mathematical Programming (PMP) literature, specifies a quadratic implicit acreage cost function. Combined with KKT conditions, this structure accommodates zero acreage decisions while allowing for a larger and more flexible regime space. However, modeling acreage decisions in isolation is insufficient: acreage, yield, and input use choices are jointly determined. Ignoring these interdependencies may yield biased parameter estimates and misleading policy simulations (Koutchadé et al., 2018, 2021).

A second major limitation of FADN data is the absence of crop-specific input use information. Variable inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides are typically observed only at the farm level. This aggregation complicates the identification of crop-level production technologies and input demand responses.

One solution within the MEMC framework adopts a two-step procedure. First, crop-level inputs are recovered using Micro-Econometric Cost Allocation (MECA) models (Just et al., 1983; Chambers and Just, 1989; Koutchadé et al., 2024). Second, these estimated inputs are treated as observed in a regime-switching MEMC system (MEMC). While computationally convenient, this sequential approach implicitly assumes that acreage and input decisions are separable. In practice, however, land allocation and input use are jointly determined under profit maximization. Sequential estimation may therefore introduce simultaneity bias and propagate measurement error into subsequent structural equations (Carpentier and Letort, 2012).

Carpentier and Letort (2012) propose a one-step MEMC framework with crop-level input allocation (MEMC-CA), integrating acreage and input decisions within a unified system. Their approach corrects for simultaneity using control functions and emphasizes the role of stochastic shocks affecting both land and input decisions. However, their framework does not explicitly account for zero acreage through regime-switching mechanisms.

A third persistent challenge concerns unobserved heterogeneity. Differences in soil quality, microclimate, machinery, managerial ability, and farmer preferences – largely unobserved in FADN – generate substantial cross-farm variation in production behavior. Ignoring this heterogeneity may

confound structural parameters with omitted characteristics.

Random parameter MEMC models provide a flexible way to address this issue by allowing behavioral parameters to vary across farms (Koutchadé et al., 2018). Yet incorporating many correlated random coefficients significantly increases computational complexity. Recent work explores factor-analytic structures to reduce dimensionality while preserving flexibility. Although promising, these approaches remain demanding when combined with endogenous regime-switching structures and high-dimensional input systems.

Taken together, the literature reveals a set of trade-offs. Censored regression models handle zero outcomes statistically but lack structural coherence. ERS models provide theoretical consistency but face computational limits when the regime space is large. Two-step cost allocation procedures address missing input data but may introduce simultaneity bias. Random parameter specifications capture heterogeneity but increase dimensionality and computational burden.

To date, no framework fully integrates: (i) endogenous regime switching under non-negativity constraints, (ii) flexible acreage substitution without restricting the regime space, (iii) simultaneous modeling of acreage and input allocation using farm-level input data, and (iv) random parameter heterogeneity within a computationally feasible likelihood-based estimation.

These gaps motivate the ERS-MEMC-CA model developed in the next section, which combines a quadratic acreage cost structure with endogenous regime determination and integrated input allocation in a unified estimation framework.

3. MODELING FRAMEWORK

We develop an Endogenous Regime Switching Micro-Econometric Multi-Crop model with Cost input Allocation (MEMC-CA). The framework jointly models crop choice, crop acreage choice, crop yield supply, and variable input use allocation at the farm level. It is designed to address three empirical challenges common in farm-level panel data: (i) zero crop acreages, (ii) missing crop-specific variable

input data, and (iii) unobserved heterogeneity in production conditions.

The model assumes that farmers maximize expected total profit subject to land and technological constraints. Zero acreage outcomes arise endogenously from the optimization problem and are handled using Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (KKT) conditions. Unobserved heterogeneity is incorporated through random farm-specific parameters. Estimation relies on a Stochastic Approximation Expectation-Maximization (SAEM) algorithm to handle the high-dimensional random parameter structure.

We assume the availability of panel data. Farmer i , $i = 1, \dots, N$, can produce a subset of $K + 1$ crops, $\mathcal{K} = \{0, 1, \dots, K\}$, from J variable inputs at time $t \in \mathcal{H}_{(i)} = \{t_{(i)}, \dots, T_{(i)}\}$, where $\mathcal{H}_{(i)}$ is the observation history of farm i .

3.1. Farm-level profit maximization

Consider that farmers choose his/her acreage vector, $\mathbf{S} = (S_k : k \in \mathcal{K})$ at time t , by maximizing his/her total expected profit under the non-negativity constraints, $S_k \geq 0$, $k \in \mathcal{K}$, and the total land use constraint, $\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} S_k = \bar{S}$:

$$(1) \quad \max_{\mathbf{S}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} S_k (\pi_{k,it}^e + \tau_{k,it}) - C_{it}(\mathbf{S}) \\ \text{s.t.} \\ S_k \geq 0, k \in \mathcal{K}, \text{ and } \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} S_k = \bar{S} \end{array} \right\},$$

where term $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^e = (\pi_{k,it}^e : k \in \mathcal{K})$ denotes expected crop returns vector that collects the main (observed) drivers of farmers' acreage choices. Term $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it} = (\tau_{k,it} : k \in \mathcal{K})$ denotes the vector of crop coupled payments. Term $C_{it}(\mathbf{S})$ denotes the implicit management cost of acreage vector \mathbf{S} . It accounts for crop fixed costs not include in $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^e$, and implicit costs related to the constraints (due to limiting quantities and quasi-fixed factors) on his acreage choice. Its specification is central for the regime-switching structure. Zero acreage outcomes emerge naturally from this constrained optimization program.

3.1.1. Quadratic Acreage Cost function and Regime structure

We specify the acreage cost function $C_{it}(\mathbf{S})$ as quadratic:

$$(2) \quad C_{it}(\mathbf{S}) = \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{c}_{it}^s + 1/2 \times \mathbf{S}' \mathbf{H}_i \mathbf{S},$$

where the term $\mathbf{c}_{it}^s = (c_{k,it}^s : k \in \mathcal{K})$ allows accounting for crop management costs while the cost matrices \mathbf{H}_i , a positive definite matrix, contains elements, which define motives of crop diversification for farmers. Here, we assume \mathbf{H}_i is farm-specific.¹

This quadratic formulation replaces the nested logit acreage cost function used in earlier work (Koutchadé et al, 2021) and allows greater flexibility in substitution pattern across crops. Concavity of the implied profit functions is imposed through parameter restrictions, \mathbf{H}_i , ensuring consistency of the optimization problem.

Let term r_{it} denote the production regime of farm i in year t . A production regime is characterized by the subset of crops with strictly positive acreage. Let Term $\mathcal{K}_{it}^+(r_{it}) \subseteq \mathcal{K}$ denotes the subset of crops actually produced in regime $r_{it} \in \mathcal{R}$ by farmer i at time t , with $\mathcal{K}_{it}^+(\mathbf{1}) = \mathcal{K}$ by convention. Term $\mathcal{K}_{it}^0(r_{it})$ denotes the subset of crops not produced in regime r_{it} .

3.1.2. Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions

The optimal solution in \mathbf{S} to problem (1), which is denoted by \mathbf{S}_{it} , is uniquely characterized by the following Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions:

$$(3) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{b}'_{k,i} \mathbf{S}_{-0,it} = (\pi_{k,it}^e - \pi_{0,it}^e) + (\tau_{k,it} - \tau_{0,it}) - (c_{k,it}^s - c_{0,it}^s) - v_{k,i} \bar{S}_{it} & \text{for } k \in \mathcal{K}_{it}^+(r_{it}) \setminus \{0\} \\ \mathbf{b}'_{\ell,i} \mathbf{S}_{-0,it} \geq (\pi_{\ell,it}^e - \pi_{0,it}^e) + (\tau_{\ell,it} - \tau_{0,it}) - (c_{\ell,it}^s - c_{0,it}^s) - v_{\ell,i} \bar{S}_{it} & \text{for } \ell \in \mathcal{K}_{it}^0(r_{it}) \end{cases}.$$

The term $\mathbf{S}_{-0,it} = (S_{k,it} : k = 1, \dots, K)$ is the column vector of crop acreages vector, \mathbf{S}_{it} , without the acreage of crop 0, $S_{0,it}$. The term $\mathbf{b}'_{k,i}$ is the k^{th} row of the $(K \times K)$ dimensional matrix

¹ It is well known that global convexity condition that involves the use of quadratic costs function could be problematic for policy simulation. Yet, assuming here the quadratic costs matrix \mathbf{H}_i is farmer or farm's specific, allows imposing local regularity at each farmer's data.

$\mathbf{B}_i = (b_{kj,i} : k=1, \dots, K \text{ and } j=1, \dots, K)$ while matrix \mathbf{B}_i and vector $\mathbf{v}_i = (v_{k,i} : k=1, \dots, K)$ are obtained from the $(K+1) \times (K+1)$ dimensional diversification matrix \mathbf{H}_i , such that:

$$(4) \quad \begin{cases} v_{k,i} = h_{k0,i} - h_{00,i} \\ b_{kj,i} = (h_{kj,i} - h_{k0,i}) - (h_{0j,i} - h_{00,i}) \end{cases} \text{ for } k=1, \dots, K \text{ and } j=1, \dots, K.$$

In what follows, we assume that $c_{0,it}^s \equiv 0$. The KKT conditions (3) can be written in matrix formulation as:

$$(5) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{B}_i^{++}(r_{it}) \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+(r_{it}) = \begin{bmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,+}(r_{it}) - \mathbf{1}_{K^+} \pi_{0,it}^e) + (\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it}^+(r_{it}) - \mathbf{1}_{K^+} \tau_{0,it}) \\ -\mathbf{c}_{it}^{s,+}(r_{it}) - \mathbf{v}_i^+(r_{it}) \bar{\mathbf{S}}_{it} \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{B}_i^{0+}(r_{it}) \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+(r_{it}) \geq \begin{bmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,0}(r_{it}) - \mathbf{1}_{K^0} \pi_{0,it}^e) + (\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it}^+(r_{it}) - \mathbf{1}_{K^0} \tau_{0,it}) \\ -\mathbf{c}_{it}^{s,0}(r_{it}) - \mathbf{v}_i^0(r_{it}) \bar{\mathbf{S}}_{it} \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \text{ and } \begin{cases} \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+(r_{it}) > \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^0(r_{it}) = \mathbf{0} \end{cases},$$

where matrix $\mathbf{B}_i^{++}(r_{it})$ is obtained from matrix \mathbf{B}_i , previously defined in equation (4), by discarding the columns and rows corresponding to the crops that are not produced in regime r_{it} . Matrix $\mathbf{B}_i^{0+}(r_{it})$ is obtained from matrix \mathbf{B}_i by discarding the columns corresponding to the crops that are not produced in regime r_{it} and rows corresponding to the crops that are produced in regime r_{it} .

In what follows, we assume that random terms $c_{k,it}^s$ can be decomposed as:

$$(6.a) \quad c_{k,it}^s = \beta_{k,i}^s + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^s)' \boldsymbol{\delta}_k^s + \varepsilon_{k,it}^s \text{ for } k \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{0\},$$

and in matrix notation as:²

$$(6.b) \quad \mathbf{c}_{it}^s = \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^s + \mathbf{Z}_{it}^s \boldsymbol{\delta}^s + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^s.$$

Term $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^s = (\beta_{k,i}^s : k \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{0\})$ is assumed farm-specific. It allows taking into account farmers' unobserved heterogeneity that affect farmers' acreage choice decisions. Terms $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^s = (\varepsilon_{k,it}^s : k \in \mathcal{K}_{-0})$ are assumed random. They allow accounting for the effects of stochastic events, not taken into account in $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^s$ and $(\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^s)' \boldsymbol{\delta}_k^s$. The model can be rewritten in compact form as follows:

² Equation (10) allows for more flexibility in modelling of the "quadratic" cost acreage model.

$$(7) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+ (r_{it}) = \mathbf{B}_i^{++} (r_{it})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,+} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{L}_{K^+} \boldsymbol{\pi}_{0,it}^e) + (\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it}^+ (r_{it}) - \mathbf{L}_{K^+} \boldsymbol{\tau}_{0,it}) \\ -\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{s,+} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{Z}_{it}^{s,+} \boldsymbol{\delta}^s - \mathbf{v}_i^+ (r_{it}) \bar{S}_{it} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^{s,+} (r_{it}) \end{bmatrix} \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^{s,0} (r_{it}) \geq \begin{bmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,0} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{L}_{K^0} \boldsymbol{\pi}_{0,it}^e) + (\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it}^0 (r_{it}) - \mathbf{L}_{K^0} \boldsymbol{\tau}_{0,it}) \\ -\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{s,0} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{Z}_{it}^{s,0} \boldsymbol{\delta}^s - \mathbf{v}_i^0 (r_{it}) \bar{S}_{it} - \mathbf{B}_i^{0+} (r_{it}) \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+ (r_{it}) \end{bmatrix} \end{cases}$$

Within a given regime, crop acreage choices $\mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+ (r_{it})$ are linear in expected gross margins $(\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,+} (r_{it}) \equiv (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{k,it}^e : k \in \mathcal{K}_{it}^+ (r_{it})))$ and coupled-payments for produced crops. However, regime selection itself is endogenous because the inequalities determining which crops are produced depend on expected returns and structural parameter. We collect the farms-specific parameters $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^s$, \mathbf{B}_i and \mathbf{v}_i in vector $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^s$.

3.2. Crop-level profit maximization

Expected gross margins, $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^e$, observed in acreage model, are unobserved. However, they depend on crop yields and variable input uses. We assume that crop production technologies can be described by a normalized quadratic production function (Carpentier and Letort, 2012):

$$(8) \quad f_{k,it}(\mathbf{x}_k) = \beta_{k,it}^y - (1/2) \times (\boldsymbol{\beta}_{k,it}^x - \mathbf{x}_k)' \mathbf{A}_{k,j}^{-1} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_{k,it}^x - \mathbf{x}_k),$$

and derive the congruent crop-level yield supply and variable input demand equations under the standard expected profit maximization assumption.

Production function $f_{k,it}(\mathbf{x}_k)$ is assumed to be increasing, concave and supermodular in variable input uses, \mathbf{x}_k . The supermodularity assumption implies that variable inputs are complementary in yield function $f_{k,it}(\mathbf{x}_k)$, in particular between pesticides and fertilizers. Term $\mathbf{A}_{k,j}$ is a positive definite matrix and it represents crop yield responses to variable inputs application.³ Thus, terms $\beta_{k,it}^y$ can be

³ It is easy to show that that the supermodularity condition implies that the off-diagonal elements of $\mathbf{A}_{k,j}^{-1}$ are negative. In the case of two variable inputs, it is needed the off-diagonal of $\mathbf{A}_{k,j}$ to be positive.

interpreted as the potentially yields of farmer i at time t for crop k while terms $\beta_{k,it}^x = (\beta_{k,j,it}^x : j \in \mathcal{J})$ are the variable input quantities required to achieve $\beta_{k,it}^y$.

Finally, it is assumed that $\beta_{k,it}^y$ and $\beta_{k,j,it}^x$ can be decomposed as, for $k \in \mathcal{K}$ and for $j \in \mathcal{J}$,

$$(9.a) \quad \beta_{k,it}^y = \beta_{k,i}^y + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^y)' \boldsymbol{\delta}_k^y + \varepsilon_{k,it}^y,$$

and

$$(9.b) \quad \beta_{k,j,it}^x = \beta_{k,j,i}^x + (\mathbf{z}_{k,j,it}^x)' \boldsymbol{\delta}_{k,j}^x + \varepsilon_{k,j,it}^x.$$

Terms $\beta_i^y \equiv (\beta_{k,i}^y : k \in \mathcal{K})$ and $\beta_i^x \equiv (\beta_{k,j,i}^x : j \in \mathcal{J} \text{ and } k \in \mathcal{K})$ are assumed positive and farm specific. This allows accounting for farmer's and farm's unobserved heterogeneity, and then, allows capturing the effects of farms' factor endowment (e.g., machinery, soil quality) and of farmers' motivations and skills. Terms ε_{it}^y and ε_{it}^x , where $\varepsilon_{it}^x = ((\varepsilon_{j,it}^x)' : j \in \mathcal{J})'$ and $\varepsilon_{j,it}^x = (\varepsilon_{k,j,it}^x : k \in \mathcal{K})$, allow accounting the effects of stochastic events, not taken into account in β_i^y , β_i^x , $(\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_k^y$ and $(\mathbf{z}_{k,j,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_{k,j}^x$. Farm-specific parameters $\beta_{k,i}^y$, $\beta_{k,j,i}^x$ and $\mathbf{A}_{k,i}$ for $k \in \mathcal{K}$ and $j \in \mathcal{J}$ are collected in \mathbf{p}_i^{yx} .

3.2.1. Yield supply, variable input use demand equations and expected gross margin

The optimal crop variable input demand equations are given by:

$$(10) \quad x_{k,j,it} = \beta_{k,j,it}^x - \mathbf{A}_{k,j,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it} (p_{k,it}^e)^{-1},$$

while the corresponding yield supply equations are:

$$(11) \quad y_{k,it} = \beta_{k,it}^y - (1/2) \times \mathbf{w}_{k,it}' \mathbf{A}_{k,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it} (p_{k,it}^e)^{-2},$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{it}^e = (p_{k,it}^e : k \in \mathcal{K})$ and $\mathbf{w}_{it} = (\mathbf{w}_{k,it}' : k \in \mathcal{K})'$, with $\mathbf{w}_{k,it} = (w_{j,k,it} : j \in \mathcal{J})$, respectively the vector of crop output prices and the vector of crop variable input prices. The term $\mathbf{A}_{k,j,i}$ denotes the j^{th} row of matrix $\mathbf{A}_{k,i}$ and the terms $p_{k,it}^e$ denotes farmers' expected crop prices⁴ at time t .

⁴ In empirical application, we will assume that the expected price is naïve, $p_{k,it}^e = p_{k,it-1}$

Given equations (10) and (11), the expected crop gross margins $\pi_{k,it}$ are defined by:

$$(12) \quad \pi_{k,it}^e = p_{k,it}^e (\beta_{k,i}^y + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_k^y) - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}} w_{k,j,it} (\beta_{k,j,i}^x + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_{k,j}^x) + 0.5 \times (p_{k,it}^e)^{-1} \mathbf{w}'_{k,it} \mathbf{A}_{k,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it}.$$

Terms $\pi_{k,it}^e$, are functions of expected crop prices and variable input prices. These functions depend on farm-specific parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^{yx}$, which will be introduced in acreage model (equation 7). We collect $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^{yx}$ and $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^s$ in the vector $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$.

3.2.2. Variable input use allocation equations

As discuss above, in many datasets, including FADN-type data, variable inputs are observed only at the farm level. The variable input j allocation problem consists in recovering the quantity of variable input j , $x_{k,j,it}$, for each crop k , farmer i and period t , based on observed crop acreages and variable input uses observed at the farm level (Koutchadé *et al.*, 2024). A simple accounting equation gives:

$$(13) \quad \bar{x}_{j,it} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} S_{k,it} \bar{S}_{it}^{-1} x_{k,j,it} + u_{j,it}^x,$$

where $\bar{x}_{j,it}$, $j \in \mathcal{J}$, denotes the vector of input use level j at farm level per ha, and term $u_{j,it}^x$ denotes the effects of measurement errors, due for example to stock variations.

Crop variable input uses, $x_{k,j,it}$, for $j \in \mathcal{J}$ and $k \in \mathcal{K}$, being unobserved, we replace them in the equation (12) by the variable input demand equation previously defined by equation (10). Combined equations (11) and (13) yields the following variable input allocation equations:⁵

$$(14) \quad \bar{x}_{j,it} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} S_{k,it} \bar{S}_{it}^{-1} \beta_{k,j,i}^x - \mathbf{A}_{k,j,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it} (p_{k,it}^e)^{-1} + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_{k,j}^x + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} S_{k,it} \bar{S}_{it}^{-1} e_{k,j,it}^x + u_{j,it}^x.$$

⁵ It should be noted that, in equation (14) we assume that we observed output price for all crops in \mathcal{K} . If we need to consider crops that prices are not observed, in allocation model, as is often the case in accountancy data, we need to augment the set \mathcal{K} by \mathcal{K}^{0th} , the set containing these crops. The cost allocation model becomes:

$$\bar{x}_{j,it} = \widehat{S}_{it}^{-1} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K} \cup \mathcal{K}^{0th}} S_{k,it} \widehat{S}_{it}^{-1} \zeta_{k,j,it}^x (\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^{yx}) + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_{k,j}^x + e_{k,j,it}^x + u_{j,it}^x$$

where $\widehat{S}_{it} = \bar{S}_{it} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}^{0th}} S_{k,it}$ and

$$\zeta_{k,j,it}^x (\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^{yx}) = \begin{cases} \beta_{k,j,i}^x - \mathbf{A}_{k,j,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it} (p_{k,it}^e)^{-1} & \text{for } k \in \mathcal{K} \\ \beta_{k,j,i}^x & \text{for } k \in \mathcal{K}^{0th} \end{cases}.$$

This formulation allows identification of crop-level variable input use parameters even when crop-level variable input data are missing. Identification relies on cross-crop and cross-farm variation in acreage shares ($S_{k,it} \bar{S}_{it}^{-1}$) and crop-specific covariates ($\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx}$), which generate differential marginal conditions across crops within the farm.⁶ These sources of variation permit recovery of the structural allocation parameters from observed farm-level totals without mechanical disaggregation.

Disturbance term $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^x$ in equation (14) captures the effects of stochastic events (*e.g.*, weather or pest realizations) influencing farmers' input use decisions during the cropping season. Because acreage choice decisions are made prior these realizations, disturbance terms in the acreage equations, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^s$, are assumed to be independent of the seasonal shocks affecting variable input allocation, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^x$.

Accordingly, we impose:

$$(15) \quad E(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^x | \mathbf{S}_{it}, \mathbf{z}_{it}^x) = E(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^x | \mathbf{S}_{it}) = \mathbf{0},$$

which ensures that the seasonal allocation shocks do not contaminate the acreage equation and preserves the recursive timing structure of decisions.

In contrast, farm-specific unobserved characteristics may simultaneously influence acreage and variable input use decisions. Ignoring this structural linkage would induce endogeneity bias, as acreage shares ($S_{k,it} \bar{S}_{it}^{-1}$) would be correlated with the farm-specific parameter $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^{yx}$ that allows embedding unobserved farmers characteristics in the input allocation equations. Joint estimation of the acreage and variable input allocation systems addresses these issues by explicitly modeling potential correlations across random parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^{yx}$ and $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^s$. This specification captures persistent differences in soil quality, managerial ability, or technology that jointly influence acreage and input use decisions.

The composite error term $\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} S_{k,it} \bar{S}_{it}^{-1} \varepsilon_{k,j,it}^x + u_{j,it}^x$ in equation (14) is inherently heteroscedastic, as its variance depends on the acreage shares across crops. Rather than modeling crop-specific seasonal

⁶ We introduce key allocations of pesticides and fertilizers in $\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx}$.

shocks separately, we assume that within-season productivity shocks affecting variable input use are largely driven by farm-level realizations that are more common across crops within a farm-year. Under this interpretation, the crop-specific composite term can be approximate by a reduced-form farm-level disturbance $u_{j,it}^x$. These disturbances are allowed to be correlated across inputs and with yield equation errors, preserving the joint nature of production decisions.

Under this specification, the crop-level variable input allocation equations simplify to:

$$(16) \quad \bar{x}_{j,it} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} s_{k,it} \bar{s}_{it}^{-1} \beta_{k,j,i}^x - \mathbf{A}_{k,j,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it} (\rho_{k,it}^e)^{-1} + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \delta_{k,j}^x + u_{j,it}^x.$$

3.3. Random parameters and unobserved heterogeneity

Farms differ in soil quality, managerial ability, machinery, and other persistent characteristics. To capture this heterogeneity, we allow key parameters ρ_i to vary across farms. Before specifying explicitly, the distribution of the random parameters ρ_i , we present its elements in detail below.

Some (unconstrained) parametrizations of random parameters are needed to account for some necessary constraints. The matrices $\mathbf{A}_{k,i}$, for $k \in \mathcal{K}$, and \mathbf{B}_i must be positive definite to guarantee the concavity of the considered crop yield functions and the convexity of the quadratic cost function.

In addition, the terms $\beta_i^y = (\beta_{k,i}^y : k \in \mathcal{K})$ and $\beta_i^x = (\beta_{k,j,i}^x : k \in \mathcal{K} \text{ and } j \in \mathcal{J})$ must be positive. Finally, the terms $\beta_i^s = (\beta_{k,i}^s : k \in \mathcal{K}_{-0})$ and $\mathbf{v}_i^s = (\mathbf{v}_{k,i}^s : k \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{0\})$ have no particular constraints, and will not be transformed.

To impose that matrices \mathbf{B}_i and $\mathbf{A}_{k,i}$ to be positive definite, we use the following decompositions⁷:

$$(17.a) \quad \mathbf{A}_{k,i} = \Delta(\boldsymbol{\zeta}_{k,i}^x) \mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_{k,i}^x) \Delta(\boldsymbol{\zeta}_{k,i}^x) \text{ for } k \in \mathcal{K},$$

$$(17.b) \quad \mathbf{B}_i = \Delta(\boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^s) \mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_i^s) \Delta(\boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^s),$$

⁷ Alternative approach involves using Log-Cholesky parameterization (Pinheiro, and Bates, 1996) which also guarantee the uniqueness of positive definite matrix. \mathbf{A} is decomposed as $\mathbf{A} = \boldsymbol{\Lambda} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}'$ where $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = (a_{mn} : m, n = 1, \dots, J)$ is a low triangular matrix, so that $a_{mn} = 0$ if $m < n$ and $a_{mm} > 0$.

where $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_{k,j}^x$, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{k,j}^x$, $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^s$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i^s$ are assumed random farm-specific. $\boldsymbol{\Delta}(\boldsymbol{\zeta})$ is a $(q \times q)$ diagonal matrix of the elements of a dimension q positive vector $\boldsymbol{\zeta}$, and $\mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\omega})$ is a $(q \times q)$ correlation matrix parametrized by $(q \times (q-1)/2)$ angles stacked in vector $\boldsymbol{\omega}$. To construct $\mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\omega})$, we use a spherical parametrization approach (Pinheiro and Bates, (1996); Lucchetti and Pedini (2023)) which combines Cholesky decomposition of $\mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \boldsymbol{\Lambda}(\boldsymbol{\omega})\boldsymbol{\Lambda}'(\boldsymbol{\omega})$ with a specific spherical parameterization of the Cholesky factor, $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}(\boldsymbol{\omega})$, where elements of $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ must belong to $]0, \pi[$ to guarantee the unicity of $\mathbf{R}(\boldsymbol{\omega})$. Enforcing that $\omega_{lp,k,i}$ belongs in $]0, \pi/2[$ in the case of two variable inputs ensures that the off-diagonal elements of $\mathbf{A}_{k,i}$ are positive, thereby ensuring that fertilizers and pesticides are complementary in the estimated crop yield functions.

We collect the random farm specific parameters in column vector $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$ such that

$$(18) \quad \boldsymbol{\rho}_i \equiv (\ln \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^y, \ln \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^x, \ln \boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^x, h_{\Phi}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_i^x), \boldsymbol{\beta}_i^s, \mathbf{v}_i^s, \ln \boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^s, h_{\Phi}(\boldsymbol{\omega}_i^s))$$

where $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^x = (\zeta_{k,j}^x : k \in \mathcal{K})$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i^x = (\omega_{k,j}^x : k \in \mathcal{K})$, and each element of $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$ belongs to $] -\infty, +\infty[$. The log-transformation $\ln(\cdot)$ forces $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^y$, $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^x$, $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^x = (\zeta_{k,j}^x : k \in \mathcal{K})$ and $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_i^s$ to be positive.⁸ The transformation $h_{\Phi}(\cdot)$ is defined such that the elements of $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ belong to $]0, \pi[$ and $h_{\Phi}(\omega_{mn}) \in] -\infty, +\infty[$.⁹

Finally, following Koutchadé *et al.*, (2018), farm-specific behavioral parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$ are modeled as:

$$(19) \quad \boldsymbol{\rho}_i = \boldsymbol{\mu} + \boldsymbol{\eta}_i \text{ with } \boldsymbol{\eta}_i \sim_{iid} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Omega})$$

where $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the vector of population means and $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ is an unrestricted variance-covariance matrix allowing correlation between elements of $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$.^{10,11}

⁸ An alternative for ensuring non-negativity is Softplus transformation ($softplus(x) = \ln(1 + e^x)$), which is widely applied across various fields of modern literature (eg., Glorot et al., 2011). It prevents numerical overflow for large values and provides a smoother behavior near to zero.

⁹ For instance, $\omega_{lp,k,it} = (0.5 + \arctan(\mu_{lp})) / \pi$ with $\mu_{lp,k,i} \in] -\infty, +\infty[$ involves $\omega_{lp,k,it} \in]0, \pi[$.

¹⁰ We can generalize this specification by allowing $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$ depending on time-constant control variables, farm or farmer characteristics. For each l element of $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$, we can retain the following specification: $\rho_{l,i} = \mu_l + \bar{\mathbf{z}}_i' \boldsymbol{\nu}_l + \eta_{l,i}$.

¹¹ Allowing $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$ to be fully unrestricted increases the number of parameters to be estimated. The SAEM algorithm used in this study is specifically designed for nonlinear mixed-effects models with high-dimensional random effects. By treating the random parameters as latent variables and iteratively approximating the complete-data likelihood, SAEM avoids repeated

3.4. Identification

Identification relies on several complementary sources of variation. First, cross-sectional and intertemporal variation in expected gross margins generates differential incentives across crops and farms. Second, observed patterns of zero and positive acreages provide information on the regime selection process and the underlying non-negativity constraints. Third, variation in input and output prices shifts relative profitability and sharpens identification of behavioral responses. Finally, the panel dimension allows separation of persistent farm-level heterogeneity from transitory shocks.

The substitution parameters embedded in the acreage cost matrix \mathbf{B}_i are identified from the responsiveness of acreages to changes in relative expected margins within observed production regimes. Regime participation frequencies, in turn, identify the variance-covariance structure of unobservable through systematic patterns of crop entry and exit.

Joint estimation of yield, variable input allocation, and acreage equations further strengthens identification by mitigating endogeneity concerns associated with expected gross margins, which are themselves functions of variable input use and productivity.

4. ESTIMATION STRATEGY

The full model (ERS-MEMC-CA) includes yield supply equations (for produced crops) and crop-level variable input allocation equations,

$$(20.a) \quad \begin{cases} y_{k,it} = \beta_{k,i}^y - (1/2) \times \mathbf{w}'_{k,it} \mathbf{A}_{k,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it} (p_{k,it}^e)^{-2} + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_{k,j}^x + \varepsilon_{k,it}^y & \text{for } k \in \mathcal{K}_{it}^+(r_{it}) \\ \bar{x}_{j,it} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} s_{k,it} \bar{s}_{it}^{-1} \beta_{k,j,i}^x - \mathbf{A}_{k,j,i} \mathbf{w}_{k,it} (p_{k,it}^e)^{-1} + (\mathbf{z}_{k,it}^{yx})' \boldsymbol{\delta}_{k,j}^x + u_{j,it}^x \end{cases},$$

acreage choice equations (for produced crops) and inequality constraints that characterize non-produced crops:

high-dimensional numerical integration. This approach improves numerical stability and reduces simulation noise compared with simulated maximum likelihood, particularly when the covariance matrix is unrestricted.

$$(20.b) \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+ (r_{it}) = \mathbf{B}_i^{++} (r_{it})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,+} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{I}_K^+ \boldsymbol{\pi}_{0,it}^e) + (\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it}^+ (r_{it}) - \mathbf{I}_K^+ \boldsymbol{\tau}_{0,it}^+) \\ -\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{s,+} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{Z}_{it}^{s,+} \boldsymbol{\delta}^s - \mathbf{v}_i^+ (r_{it}) \bar{\mathbf{S}}_{it} - \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^{s,+} (r_{it}) \end{bmatrix} \\ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^{s,0} (r_{it}) \geq \begin{bmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,0} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{I}_K^0 \boldsymbol{\pi}_{0,it}^e) + (\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it}^0 (r_{it}) - \mathbf{I}_K^0 \boldsymbol{\tau}_{0,it}^0) \\ -\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{s,0} (r_{it}) - \mathbf{Z}_{it}^{s,0} \boldsymbol{\delta}^s - \mathbf{v}_i^0 (r_{it}) \bar{\mathbf{S}}_{it} - \mathbf{B}_i^{0+} (r_{it}) \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+ (r_{it}) \end{bmatrix} \end{cases},$$

and random parameters distribution, that capture farm-level unobserved heterogeneity:

$$(20.c) \quad \boldsymbol{\rho}_i = (\boldsymbol{\rho}_i^{yx}, \boldsymbol{\rho}_i^s) \sim_{iid} \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}),$$

where $\mathbf{Z}_{it}^{y,+}$ and \mathbf{Z}_{it}^x are well defined as previously.

We assume that the unobserved shocks affecting yield and variable input use decisions

$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^{yx} \equiv ((\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^y)', (\mathbf{u}_{it}^x)')$, and acreage choice decisions $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^s$, are jointly normally distributed:

$$(21) \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^{yx} \sim_{iid} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{yx}) \text{ and } \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^s \sim_{iid} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^s),$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^s$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{yx}$ are unrestricted covariance matrix. In addition, we assume that $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^{yx}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^s$ are independent conditionally on the random parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$.¹²

Our aim is to estimate the (population) parameters collected in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, \boldsymbol{\delta}^y, \boldsymbol{\delta}^x, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{yx}, \boldsymbol{\delta}^s, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^s)$, where

$\boldsymbol{\theta}^y \equiv (\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ characterizes the distribution of the random parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$, $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{yx} \equiv (\boldsymbol{\delta}^y, \boldsymbol{\delta}^x, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{yx})$

parameterizes the yield supply and crop-level variable input allocation equations given $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$, and

$\boldsymbol{\theta}^s \equiv (\boldsymbol{\delta}^s, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^s)$ parametrizes the acreage choice equations given $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$. Finally, let define $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs} = (\boldsymbol{\theta}^{yx}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^s)$.

4.1. SAEM algorithm

Estimation follows the likelihood-based framework developed in Koutchadé et al. (2021). We treat the

farm-specific parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$ as “missing” data, and estimate the model using a Stochastic

Approximation Expectation-Maximization (SAEM) algorithm. Let the complete data consist of the

observed outcome (acreage, yields, and crop-level variable input allocation), $(\mathbf{y}_{it}^+, \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{it}, \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+, \mathbf{S}_{it}^0, \mathbf{z}_{it})$, and

¹² This assumption makes sense as farmers’ crop acreage decisions precedes the realization of $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^{yx}$, the stochastic events that affect the yields obtained and the variable inputs used. Indeed, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{it}^{yx}$ capture the effects of stochastic events influencing farmers’ input use and yield decisions during the cropping season. These events are thus unknown to farmers at the time of acreage choices, in the planting season, implying that they are independent of crop acreages decisions.

the vector of “missing” data $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$, for $i=1,\dots,N$ and for $t \in \mathcal{H}_{(i)}$. The complete data log-likelihood function is the sample log-likelihood function of the joint model of the dependent variable, $\boldsymbol{\chi}_{it} \equiv (\mathbf{y}_{it}^+, \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{it}, \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+, \mathbf{S}_{it}^0)$, and “missing” data, $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$, given the exogenous variables of the model, \mathbf{z}_{it} , for $t \in \mathcal{H}_{(i)}$ for $i=1,\dots,N$. The contribution of individual i in the complete data log-likelihood function at $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ of the model is given by:

$$(22) \quad \ell_i^c(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{H}_{(i)}} \ln f(\boldsymbol{\chi}_{it} | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs}) + \log \varphi(\boldsymbol{\rho}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}; \boldsymbol{\Omega})$$

where $f(\boldsymbol{\chi}_{it} | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs})$ denotes the joint distribution of the dependent variable conditional on farm-specific parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$, and $\varphi(\boldsymbol{\rho}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}; \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ is the probability density function of random parameters $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$. The complete-data likelihood function naturally separates into two components: (i) a structural “kernel/core” model governed by parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs}$ and $\boldsymbol{\theta}^s$, which determines the behavioral relationships between acreage, yields, and crop-level variable input allocation conditional on $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i$; and (ii) a mixing distribution governed by $\boldsymbol{\theta}^p$, which characterizes the population distribution of unobserved heterogeneity. This additive decomposition implies that estimation can be partitioned into updates of structural parameters and updates of the mixing distribution, as in Koutchadé et al. (2021).

A key feature of the acreage choice model is that acreage choice decisions satisfy KKT conditions. The non-negativity constraints on acreage generate inequality restrictions that determine whether a crop is produced or not. As a consequence, the likelihood contribution of the acreage system involves probabilities defined over truncated multivariate normal regions. The conditional observed likelihood $f(\boldsymbol{\chi}_{it} | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs})$ can be decomposed as:

$$(23) \quad f(\boldsymbol{\chi}_{it} | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs}) = f(\mathbf{y}_{it}^+, \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{it} | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs}) \times f(\mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+ | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s) \times \Pr(\mathbf{S}_{it}^0 = \mathbf{0} | \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+, \boldsymbol{\rho}_i; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s)$$

where $f(\mathbf{y}_{it}^+, \bar{\mathbf{x}}_{it} | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^{yxs})$ is a multivariate normal density function for the yield and crop-level variable input allocation equations, and $f(\mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+ | \boldsymbol{\rho}_i, \mathbf{z}_{it}; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s)$ is a multivariate normal density function for the acreage equations. Their dimensions vary with the number of produced crops. Finally, term

$\Pr(\mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^0 = \mathbf{0} | \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+, \boldsymbol{\rho}_i; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s)$ is a conditional probability based on the conditional distribution of the error term of acreage model for non-produced crops, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^{s,0}(r_{it})$, in the error term of acreage model for produced crops, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^{s,+}(r_{it})$. Term $\Pr(\mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^0 = \mathbf{0} | \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+, \boldsymbol{\rho}_i; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s)$ corresponds to a multivariate normal cumulative distribution function (CDF) ensuring that non-produced crops satisfy the KKT inequalities describe in equation (20.b).

$$(24.a) \quad \Pr(\mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^0 = \mathbf{0} | \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+, \boldsymbol{\rho}_i; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s) = \Pr \left[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^{s,0}(r_{it}) \geq \boldsymbol{\xi}_{it}^{s,0+}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_i, r_{it}) | \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+, \boldsymbol{\rho}_i; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s \right] \\ = 1 - \Pr \left[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^{s,0}(r_{it}) \leq \boldsymbol{\xi}_{it}^{s,0+}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_i, r_{it}) | \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{it}^{s,+}(r_{it}), \boldsymbol{\rho}_i; \boldsymbol{\theta}^s \right]$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi}_{it}^{s,0+}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_i, r_{it})$ is well defined by equation (20.b):

$$(24.b) \quad \boldsymbol{\xi}_{it}^{s,0+}(\boldsymbol{\rho}_i, r_{it}) = \left[\begin{array}{c} (\boldsymbol{\pi}_{it}^{e,0}(r_{it}) - \boldsymbol{\iota}_K^0 \boldsymbol{\tau}_{0,it}^e) + (\boldsymbol{\tau}_{it}^0(r_{it}) - \boldsymbol{\iota}_K^0 \boldsymbol{\tau}_{0,it}^0) \\ -\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^{s,0}(r_{it}) - \mathbf{Z}_{it}^{s,0} \boldsymbol{\delta}^s - \mathbf{v}_i^0(r_{it}) \bar{\mathbf{S}}_{it} - \mathbf{B}_i^{0+}(r_{it}) \mathbf{S}_{-0,it}^+(r_{it}) \end{array} \right]$$

We evaluate these multivariate normal probabilities using the Geweke–Hajivassiliou–Keane (GHK) simulator. This approach ensures consistent treatment of corner solutions and preserves the structural interpretation of regime selection implied by the KKT conditions. The presence of inequality constraints increases the dimensionality and nonlinearity of the likelihood, which makes efficient simulation of the latent random effects particularly important.

The main departure from Koutchadé et al. (2021) concerns the simulation step of the SAEM algorithm. The conditional distribution of $\boldsymbol{\rho}_i | (\boldsymbol{\chi}_{it}, \mathbf{z}_{it} : t \in \mathcal{H}_{(i)})$ has no closed form due to (i) the non-linear structure of the model and (ii) the truncated likelihood induced by the KKT conditions. The simulation (S) step therefore requires sampling from a high-dimensional, nonstandard posterior distribution.

Rather than relying on a standard Metropolis–Hastings scheme, we implement recent advances in SAEM algorithms that improve convergence and reduce sensitivity to local maxima. Specifically, we adopt: (i) the stochastic approximation framework of Allasonnière and Chevallier (2021), which enhances exploration of the parameter space and mitigates convergence to suboptimal local maxima; (ii) the fast SAEM implementation proposed by Karimi, Lavielle, and Moulines (2020), which accelerates convergence in nonlinear mixed-effects models by combining stochastic approximation

with an efficient Metropolis–Hastings proposal strategy tailored to high-dimensional random effects. These modifications affect only the simulation (S) step of the SAEM algorithm, the stochastic approximation and maximization steps remain structurally identical to those in Koutchadé et al. (2021).

Together, the GHK evaluation of truncated normal probabilities and the enhanced SAEM simulation scheme allow consistent and computationally feasible estimation of the full regime-switching multi-crop model with inequality constraints and correlated random effects.

5. EMPIRICAL APPLICATION

5.1. Data source and sample construction

The empirical application relies on farm-level data from grain producers located in the North-East of France, one of the main arable crop production areas in the country. The dataset was provided by a farm accounting agency located in the French administrative department of *La Marne* and is comparable in structure to data collected within the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN).

The dataset consists of an unbalanced panel of farms observed over the period 2007-2014. For each farm and year, the data provide detailed information on: crop acreages, crop yields, farm-gate output prices¹³, expenditures on fertilizers and pesticides.

Expected output prices are approximated using lagged crop prices, reflecting the assumption that farmers base their production decisions on price information observed in previous periods. Input price indices (base year 2010 = 1) are obtained at the regional level from the French Ministry of Agriculture. These indices reflect the evolution of the main production costs associated with machinery services, fuel, and hired labor. All monetary variables are deflated using the price index of hired production services in order to express values in real terms.

¹³ When a farmer does not produce a crop, the corresponding output prices are unobserved. These missing prices were estimated by the yearly average of the corresponding observed prices.

Climatic variables are obtained from Météo-France, the French national meteorological service, at the municipality level. Using these data, we compute crop-specific Growing Degree Days (GDD) indicators capturing temperature conditions during the growing season, together with cumulative precipitation measures that reflect rainfall during the relevant crop growth periods.

To ensure sufficient time variation in production decisions, we restrict the sample to farms observed for at least three consecutive years. After cleaning the original dataset and applying these restrictions, the final estimation sample contains 5,299 farm-year observations corresponding to 1,083 farms, representing approximately 87 percent of the observations available in the original dataset. We assume that farm attrition is exogenous.

The analysis focuses on seven major crops (or crop aggregates) that represent more than 80 percent of the total cultivated acreage in the study region: sugar beet, alfalfa, peas, rapeseed, winter crops (winter wheat and winter barley), maize and spring barley. The remaining cultivated area is grouped into a residual category labeled “other crops.”

A production regime is defined as the combination of crops produced by a farm in a given year. In the estimation sample, we identify approximately 55 distinct production regimes. However, the distribution of regimes is highly skewed. Many regimes are rarely observed, while a relatively small number of regimes account for the majority of observations. For example, the 15 most frequently observed regimes represent about 4,247 observations (out of 5,299) in the sample.

Table 1 provides descriptive statistics. Winter wheat is produced in almost all farms and therefore serves as the reference crop in the acreage allocation system. The average acreage shares vary from one crop to another, and crops with large shares have generally high production frequency (*e.g.*, winter wheat and rapeseed).

Table 1 Descriptive statistics

	Winter wheat	Corn	Spring Barley	Sugarbeet	Alfalfa	Protein pea	Rapeseed
Production frequency	100%	36.14%	86.54%	79.95%	60.31%	26.20%	91.71%
Average acreage share^a	0.43 (0.13)	0.05 (0.09)	0.15 (0.10)	0.13 (0.09)	0.07 (0.06)	0.02 (0.04)	0.16 (0.08)
Average acreage share^a if produced^a	0.43 (0.13)	0.13 (0.11)	0.18 (0.09)	0.16 (0.07)	0.11 (0.04)	0.07 (0.04)	0.17 (0.07)
Average gross margin (€/ha)^{a,b}	871 (310)	912 (458)	814 (295)	1784d (421)	605 (286)	730 (304)	853 (421)
Average yield (t/ha)^a	8.51b (1.03)	9.32 (1.89)	6.6.91 (1.22)	93.06 (13.06)	12.33 (2.15)	4.69 (1.21)	3.84 (0.66)
Average price (€/t)^a	157b (33)	134 (37)	164 (34)	26c (4)	80 (17)	211 (50)	346 (73)
Average fertilization costs	234 (61)	193 (55)	179 (50)	290 (93)	269 (106)	84 (42)	231 (62)
Average crop protection costs^a	185 (42)	110 (37)	107 (29)	263 (68)	63 (28)	155 (45)	207 (54)

a. Empirical standard deviation in parentheses, b. Off-quota price of sugar beet.

A key feature of the dataset is that it contains information on both crop-level input use and aggregated farm-level input expenditures. While total expenditures on fertilizers and pesticides are recorded at the farm level, crop-level input applications are also available. This dual information allows us to evaluate the performance of alternative modeling strategies.

In particular, we compare three specifications: a model including observed crop-level input demand equations (ERS-MEMC-MI), the proposed ERS-MEMC-CA one-step approach, which jointly estimates acreage, yield, and input allocation decisions using aggregated farm-level variable input expenditures, and a two-step procedure, in which crop-level inputs are first predicted – using the model MECA developed in Koutchadé et al. (20024) – and subsequently used in the variable input demand equations of ERS-MEMC-MI framework.

This comparison provides a useful benchmark to assess the ability of the ERS-MEMC-CA framework to recover crop-level variable input allocation behavior when only aggregated farm-level variable input data are available.

5.2. Estimation procedure implementation

This section presents the estimation results of the random parameter ERS-MEMC-CA model described above. The estimated specification includes 77 random parameters, capturing unobserved heterogeneity across farms in the yield, variable input allocation, and acreage equations. These random parameters are assumed to follow a multivariate normal distribution with an unrestricted variance-covariance matrix. Estimation is implemented using the *qrpmulticropest* R package, which operationalizes the estimation procedure described in Section 4. In particular, the function *qrp_model_yxs_ca* implements the SAEM algorithm for the random parameter ERS-MEMC-CA model and provides several tools for monitoring convergence (convergence graphs).

The estimation relies on a Stochastic Approximation Expectation–Maximization (SAEM) algorithm. In the S-step of the algorithm, the conditional distribution of the random effects is simulated using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) procedure based on the efficient Metropolis-Hastings proposal strategy proposed by Karimi and Lavielle (2019). At each iteration, 300 simulation draws are generated for each farm, including 100 burn-in draws.

Because acreage decisions are derived from Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (KKT) optimality conditions, the likelihood function involves evaluating multivariate truncated normal probabilities associated with the non-negativity constraints on crop acreages. These probabilities are approximated using the Geweke–Hajivassiliou–Keane (GHK) simulator, based on 500 Sobol quasi-random draws, which provide efficiently simulates high-dimensional truncated normal distributions.

The SAEM algorithm proceeds in two stages. In the first stage, the algorithm explores the parameter space without memory in order to escape potential local maxima, following the strategy proposed by Allasonnière and Chevallier (2021). During this exploration phase, the algorithm rapidly approaches the neighborhood of the maximum likelihood estimator.

In the second stage – the smoothing phase – the algorithm is run for up to 300 additional iterations, during which the stochastic approximation step size decreases and the parameter estimates stabilize. Convergence is assessed using standard SAEM diagnostics, including the stabilization of parameter

trajectories and the convergence of the simulated likelihood.

Finally, all control variables included in the model are centered prior to estimation in order to improve numerical stability.

5.3. Estimation results

The estimated values of the main parameters characterizing the mean of the random parameter distributions for the yield supply, variable input allocation, and acreage choice equations are reported in Tables 2 and 3. The complete set of estimation results is available from the authors upon request. Overall, the results indicate that most parameters – including the means and standard deviations of the random coefficients – are precisely estimated. This provides strong evidence that unobserved farm heterogeneity plays a significant role in explaining farmers’ production behavior.

From an economic perspective, variations in farm-specific parameters reflects persistent differences across farms in production technologies, management practices, soil quality, and risk attitudes. These structural differences imply persistent heterogeneity in crop yields, variable input intensities, and acreage choice decisions. Accounting for this heterogeneity is therefore essential for accurately capturing farmers’ responses to economic incentives and agronomic conditions.

Furthermore, the estimated correlations between random parameters (not reported here for brevity) are statistically significant both within and across the different subsystems (acreage, variable input and yield) of the model. These correlations indicate that acreage choices, variable input use, and yield outcomes are jointly determined within the production system. This finding highlights the importance of modeling these decisions within an integrated framework, as treating them separately would likely lead to biased estimated due to the endogeneity of expected gross margins in acreage equations and endogeneity of acreage in variable input allocation equations.

Overall, the results confirm that farmers’ decisions regarding crop choices, acreage choices, variable input intensity, and expected profitability are closely interconnected and shaped by persistent farm-specific characteristics.

Table 2 Selected estimated parameters of yield and input models

	Potential Yield (ton/ha)	Fertilizer requirement (100 euro/ha)	Pesticides requirement (100euro/ha)	Input use flexibility $A_{k,i}$		
	$\beta_{k,i}^y$	$\beta_{k,1,i}^x$	$\beta_{k,2,i}^x$	Fertilizer	Pesticide	Fertilizer x Pesticide
Winter wheat	8.82***	2.79***	2.19***	0.44***	0.52***	0.59***
Corn	9.83***	2.10***	1.48***	0.15***	0.95***	0.98***
Spring Barley	7.26***	1.97***	1.49***	0.79***	0.37***	0.25***
Alfalfa	12.89***	4.02***	0.91***	0.30***	0.56***	0.09***
Protein pea	5.09***	2.06***	1.83***	0.48***	0.37***	0.46***
Rape-seed	3.96***	2.73***	2.57***	0.71***	0.17***	0.49***
Sugar beet(10t/ha)	9.40***	3.57***	3.24***	0.85***	0.80***	0.62***
Other crops		1.75***	2.47***			

From a policy perspective, these findings imply that agricultural and environmental policies affecting variable input prices or crop profitability are likely to generate simultaneous adjustments in both variable input intensities and acreage choice decisions. Consequently, policy evaluations that consider only one margin of adjustment – such as variable input demand or acreage choices alone – may underestimate the overall behavioral response of farmers. In the yield supply and variable input allocation models, four groups of parameters characterize crop production technologies: potential yield levels, fertilizer requirements, pesticide requirements, and the flexibility matrix governing fertilizers and pesticide uses for each crop. Table 2 reports the corresponding estimates and provides insights into crop-specific production technologies.

For instance, the estimated maximum yield for winter wheat is approximately 8.82 tons per hectare, with an associated fertilizer expenditure of 279 euros per hectare at the optimum. The estimated parameters governing fertilizer and pesticide use are consistent with agronomic expectations. In particular, sugar beet is estimated to require substantially higher pesticide expenditures than wheat, barley, protein crops, and alfalfa. Finally, the estimated parameters governing the distribution of the price effects, $A_{k,i}$, ensure that, for each crop, the production function remain concave and the fertilizer and pesticide uses are complementary, as implied by the underlying production technology.

From an economic perspective, the result highlights the presence of substantial technological heterogeneity across crops. Differences in potential yields and variable input requirements imply that farmers face crop specific production technologies when allocating acreages and variables inputs. The strong pesticide requirements estimated for sugar beet are consistent with agronomic knowledge and indicate that environmental regulations targeting chemical inputs may have heterogeneous impacts across crops. Moreover, the estimated complementarity between fertilizers and pesticides suggests that input use decisions are jointly determined, implying that policies affecting one input may generate indirect adjustments in the use of other inputs.

Table 3 Selected estimated parameters of acreage model

	Fixed cost (100 euro/ha) $\beta_{k,i}^s - \beta_{0,i}^s$	$v_{k,i}$	Diagonal elements of \mathbf{B}_i
Winter wheat	-	-	-
Corn	0.17***	0.13***	1.62***
Spring Barley	0.12	-0.20***	1.79***
Alfalfa	-0.24***	-0.02	1.94***
Protein pea	-0.12	0.16***	1.38***
Rape-seed	0.16***	-0.26***	1.77***
Sugar beet	-0.31***	-0.21***	2.26***

In the acreage choice equations, two sets of parameters characterize the implicit cost of managing acreage choices: crop-specific fixed costs $\beta_{k,it}^s$ and acreage cost matrix \mathbf{H}_i , governing adjustment in acreage choice across crops. Because the acreage choice system is identified in relative terms, only differences in fixed cost across crops are identifiable, rather than their absolute levels. Accordingly, Table 3 reports the estimated fixed cost differentials, $\beta_{k,it}^s - \beta_{0,it}^s$ relative to the reference crop, winter wheat.

The result suggests that, on average, winter wheat involves lower management and adjustment cost compared to most alternative crops. For instance, corn and rapeseed exhibit positive fixed cost differentials, suggesting higher crop-specific management costs relative to winter wheat. In contrast,

crops such as alfalfa, protein peas, and sugar beet display negative differentials, indicating lower fixed management costs relative to the reference crop. Economically, these differences may reflect crop-specific requirements in terms of machinery use, labor organization, or agronomic management practices.

The acreage cost matrix \mathbf{H}_i is not directly identifiable by the system. Instead, the estimation identifies the transformed parameter \mathbf{B}_i and \mathbf{v}_i . Specifically, the element of matrix \mathbf{B}_i and vector \mathbf{v}_i are defined as $\mathbf{B}_{i,kj} = \mathbf{H}_{i,kj} - \mathbf{H}_{i,k0} - (\mathbf{H}_{i,0j} - \mathbf{H}_{i,00})$ and $\mathbf{v}_{i,k} = \mathbf{H}_{i,k0} - \mathbf{H}_{i,00}$ where crop 0 correspond to the reference crop. This normalization removes the non-identifiable components of the cost function \mathbf{H}_i , while preserving the economically relevant marginal adjustment cost of reallocation of acreage across crops.

The diagonal elements of matrix \mathbf{B}_i , reported in Table 3, measure the marginal cost of expanding the acreage of each crop relative to the reference crop. These coefficients are positive and statistically significant for most crops, implying that the marginal cost of increasing acreage rises with the scale of production. Economically, this reflects increasing management complexity and agronomic constraints, such as crop rotation requirements or machinery limitations, which discourage excessive specialization and promote crop diversification within farms.

Finally, the estimated distribution of the parameters defining matrix \mathbf{B}_i ensures that the implied quadratic cost matrix is positive definite, thereby guaranteeing the convexity of the acreage cost function and consistent land allocation behavior.

Economically, this normalization reflects the fact that farmers make land allocation decisions based on relative profitability and relative management costs across crops, rather than on the absolute level of these costs. The transformed parameters therefore retain all economically relevant information needed to characterize crop allocation behavior.

This result confirms that the quadratic acreage cost specification provides a flexible way to capture the agronomic and managerial constraints underlying observed crop diversification patterns.

The significance of several off-diagonal elements highlights that acreage decisions are shaped not only by crop-specific profitability but also by interactions among crops within the farm production system.

1.1. Calibrated models, goodness of fit and price elasticities

1.1.1. Calibration of the farm-specific models

Once the population parameters of the model, θ , are estimated, we can “statistically calibrate” the farm-specific random coefficients ρ_i and the disturbance of the acreage choice model, ϵ_{it}^s . This calibration framework generates a set of farm-specific models, and allows the model to reproduce the observed production regimes and acreage choice in the baseline situation. It can then be used to “predict” crop-level variable input uses, \mathbf{x}_{it} , yields, \mathbf{y}_{it} , acreages, \mathbf{S}_{it} , and regime production, r_{it} , for each farmer and time period, under alternative economic conditions, including changes in output prices, input prices, or policy payments.

The calibration of the random terms, ρ_i and ϵ_{it}^s proceeds as follows. Firstly, following Koutchadé et al. (2018, 2021), the farm-specific parameter vector $\hat{\rho}_i$ is calibrated as the mode of its simulated conditional distribution given the observed data. Second, we recover disturbances ϵ_{it}^s in acreage choice model for produced and non-produced crops. For crops with positive observed acreage, the disturbance terms are directly recovered from the equality conditions implied by the KKT optimality conditions. These conditions ensure that the marginal profitability of each produced crop equals the shadow value of land. For crops that are not produced, the disturbance terms must satisfy the inequality conditions implied by the non-negativity constraints on acreage. These conditions ensure that the marginal profitability of these crops remains below the shadow value of land. Conditional on the observed production regime, the disturbance vector follows a multivariate normal distribution truncated by the KKT inequality conditions. We therefore simulate draws from this truncated distribution and compute the mean of these admissible draws to obtain the calibrated disturbance vector.

5.3.1. Goodness of fit

This calibrated framework is then used to compute the goodness-of-fit indicators, evaluate regime choice probabilities, and derive the price elasticities of input use, yield supply, and acreage choice.

Table 4 presents the Sim-R² criterion, which measures the ability of the estimated model to reproduce observed farmer decisions. The Sim-R² is obtained by regressing the observed values on the model-predicted values. For the ERS-MEMC-CA specification, the resulting Sim-R² values range from 26% to 99%, indicating that the model provides a satisfactory fit to the observed production decisions in the data.

Table 4 Fitting criteria for yield supply and variable input allocation equations

	Acreage model Without regime change	Yield model	Input allocation model	
			Fertilizers	Pesticides
	Sim-R2	Sim-R2	Sim-R2	Sim-R2
Winter wheat	---	55.11%	69.12%	82.79%
Corn	91.47%	51.01%		
Spring Barley	81.89%	39.29%		
Alfalfa	95.67%	26.33%		
Protein peas	77.42%	50.07%		
Rape-seed	91.08%	47.60%		
Sugar beet	98.49%	58.63%		

5.4. Statistical comparison with alternative models and estimation approaches

To evaluate the performance of the proposed approach, we compare three triplets of data set, model specification and estimation strategy: (i) the one-step estimation of the MEMC-CA model, presented above, which jointly estimates acreage, yield, and variable input allocation equations when crop-level input data are not observed; (ii) a specification that directly estimates the MEMC model using observed crop-level input data; and (iii) a two-step procedure, in which crop-level input allocations are first estimated using a MECA model (Koutchadé et al., 2024) and then used in the MEMC

framework (CA+MEMC). This comparison allows us to assess the ability of the proposed one-step approach to recover crop-level input allocation behavior when only farm-level input data are available. Tables 5 and 6 show the average estimated fertilizer and pesticide use for each crop across all models. These estimates fall within a reasonable range compared to the sample averages of crop variable input use. In addition, the tables include the estimated Sim-R² criteria, which indicate that the proposed models provide a satisfactory fit to the data. The results show that the MEMC (single step) model provides the most accurate predictions for all outputs, outperforming the other approaches. However, in cases where information on input use by crop is not available, the proposed approach in this paper (MEMC – CA) proves to be superior to both the MECA and the two-step methods. This is true even for less commonly produced crops, where the proposed method and other approaches are evaluated. Yet, if model validation results shows that the CA+MEMC and MEMC-CA specifications perform well in predicting crop choice and production regimes, particularly in reproducing zero acreage outcomes, as well as (expected) yield levels, they also tend to show that these specifications perform poorly regarding allocation of variable input to crops. More precisely, the quality estimated crop-specific allocation is not sufficient for the calibrated simulation models to provide reliable results for policy directly targeting uses of variable inputs, such as pesticide and/or fertilizer taxes. Yet, the calibrated simulation models can provide reliable results for policies targeting acreage choices, such as area-based coupled payments.

Table 5 Average of predicted and observed fertilizer uses

Fertilizers														
	MEMC (single step)			MEMC-CA (single step)			CA+MEMC (two steps)			Observed sample		MECA		
	Sim-R2	Estimated		Sim-R2	Estimated		Sim-R2	Estimated				Sim-R2	Estimated	
	(%)	Mean	Std Dev	(%)	Mean	Std Dev	(%)	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	(%)	Mean	Std Dev
Winter wheat	43	234	25	21	222	69	31	204	25	234	61	71	202	52
Corn	35	194	23	03	139	68	20	195	26	194	55	45	193	39
Spring Barley	49	178	22	18	137	71	16	157	19	179	50	25	157	28
Alfalfa	46	270	46	14	317	100	02	380	74	269	106	24	380	121
Protein pea	56	81	24	03	195	82	05	108	19	084	42	0.10	108	25
Rape-seed	49	232	25	01	200	52	17	243	33	231	62	46	242	51
Sugar beet	42	292	38	05	389	108	17	352	81	290	93	47	352	112

Sim-R2 is the correlation between model prediction and observed variable input at crop level

Table 6 Average of predicted and observed pesticide uses

Crop protection														
	MEMC (single step)			MEMC – CA (single step)			CA+MEMC (two steps)			Observed sample		MECA		
	Sim-R2	Estimated		Sim-R2	Estimated		Sim-R2	Estimated				Sim-R2	Estimated	
	(%)	Mean	Std Dev	(%)	Mean	Std Dev	(%)	Mean	Std Dev	Mean	Std Dev	(%)	Mean	Std Dev
Winter wheat	64	185	25	23	185	29	26	180	33	185	42	41	179	39
Corn	55	112	22	07	112	57	01	89	13	110	37	03	89	16
Spring Barley	52	108	16	08	90	38	12	106	17	107	30	17	106	22
Alfalfa	37	62	13	04	80	33	01	03	0.1	63	28	0.1	03	0.49
Protein pea	61	160	29	06	85	52	04	157	45	155	46	05	158	53
Rape-seed	60	205	31	18	185	49	16	228	41	207	54	24	227	49
Sugar beet	59	261	39	14	263	59	10	293	73	263	68	17	292	89

Sim-R2 is the correlation between model prediction and observed variable input at crop level

6. CONCLUSION

Agri-environmental policies increasingly aim to regulate the use of variable agricultural inputs, such as fertilizers and pesticides. Evaluating the impact of these policies requires models that capture how farmers decide on crops, acreage, and variable inputs, considering the interdependence of these decisions and land as quasi-fixed input. Micro-econometric multi-crop (MEMC) models are commonly used in Europe with farm-level panel data but face several empirical challenges, including lacking cost accounting data (which is the case for FADN data), frequent null crop acreages and unobserved heterogeneity across farm(er)s. Existing approaches usually only address part of these issues (e.g., Koutchadé et al, 2021). Some models handle discrete crop choices, but they are computationally complex. Others incorporate heterogeneity, but they sacrifice tractability. The lack of detailed variable input data makes identifying production behavior difficult, regarding uses of agrochemicals in particular. To overcome these limitations, we propose a new structural model, the Endogenous Regime Switching Micro-Econometric Multi-Crop Model with Cost Input Allocation (MEMC-CA) and assess its empirical performances based on French farm dataset. This model can be used to analyze farmers' decisions regarding crop acreages choice, yield levels and variable input uses (pesticides and fertilizers).

Along the lines of Carpentier and Letort (2012, 2014), the basic modelling framework model integrates three interrelated components: (i) a system of crop acreage choice equations based on an acreage management cost function, (ii) a system of crop yield supply equations, and (iii) a system of variable input demand allocation equations. Crop yield supply and variable input demand equations are derived from quadratic yield functions. Acreage choice equations are derived from a quadratic acreage management cost function, as in Positive Mathematical Programming (PMP) models based on the so-called “PMP term”.

Two options are available for dealing with the lack of cost accounting data. The first option involves two steps. First, agrochemicals costs are allocated to the crops of the farms using the (CA, for cost allocation) approach proposed by Koutchadé et al (2024). This two-step modelling framework is called

the CA+MEMC model for simplicity. Second, the estimated crop-specific agrochemicals are added to the initial dataset for estimating the MEMC model. The second option consists of replacing the agrochemicals demand equation system of the ERS-MEMC model by the variable input allocation equations considered in the CA approach of Koutchadé et al (2024). The resulting model, the MEMC-CA model, is estimated in one step, based on an approach similar to the one employed for estimating the MEMC model.

Based on the estimated models, farm-specific parameters and acreage equation disturbances can be calibrated to build a simulation model consisting in a sample of farm-specific PMP type acreage choice models with flexible crop-specific input and yield levels. These “statistically” calibrated models enable policy simulations that account for joint adjustments in crop acreages, yield supplies and variable input demands at the farm level.

Importantly, the micro-econometric modelling framework we develop, the CA+MEMC and MEMC-CA models and the congruent estimation approaches, could be considered for improving the IFM-CAP model. These models are specified so as to be estimated based on FADN data. They could be used for (i) “statistically” calibrating the IFM-CAP model at the farm level and (ii) incorporating crop yield supply and input demand equation in this widely used EU-wide micro-founded farm supply model.

The empirical application employs an unbalanced panel comprising 1,083 arable farms in northeastern France, observed from 2007 to 2014. The data provide detailed information on crop acreage, yield, price, and variable input use. Seven main crops are considered, representing the majority of cultivated land. Climate variables are constructed using growing degree days (GDD) and cumulative precipitation indicators. The estimation results indicate that the MEMC model provides a good fit for the observed data and captures key features of farmers’ production behavior. Most parameters, including the means and standard deviations of the random coefficients, are precisely estimated, highlighting the importance of unobserved heterogeneity across farms. A key finding is that acreage allocation and variable input use are jointly determined with strong complementarities across inputs. Consequently,

policies targeting a single margin, such as taxes on pesticides or fertilizers, are likely to generate indirect adjustments in other inputs and crop choices. For example, a pesticide tax could reduce pesticide use, affect fertilizer application, and induce shifts toward less input-intensive crops.

Model validation shows that the CA+MEMC and MEMC-CA specifications perform well in predicting crop choice and production regimes, particularly in reproducing zero acreage outcomes, as well as (expected) yield levels. However, validation results tend to show that these specifications perform poorly regarding allocation of variable input to crops. More precisely, the quality estimated crop-specific allocation is not sufficient for the calibrated simulation models to provide reliable results for policy directly targeting uses of variable inputs, such as pesticide and/or fertilizer taxes. Yet, the calibrated simulation models can provide reliable results for policies targeting acreage choices, such as area-based couple payments.

We haven't considered policy simulations until now. We devoted most of our research effort to methodological topics. In particular, we are currently trying to improve the empirical performances of our variable input cost allocation approaches. We follow two avenues. The first one consists of testing alternatives to the cost allocation equations considered in Koutchadé et al (2024). The second one consists of incorporating the information provided by available agronomic references (e.g., recommended loads of fertilizers per crop) in the econometric cost allocation equations. This second approach yields promising results for fertilizer uses. Agronomic references for pesticide uses are more difficult to uncover.

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APPENDIX 1

Table 7 Fitting criteria for yield supply and variable input allocation equations, MEMC (single step)

	Acreage model	Yield model	Fertilizers model	Pesticides model
	Sim-R2 (%)	Sim-R2 (%)	Sim-R2 (%)	Sim-R2 (%)
Winter wheat	---	55	43	64
Corn	91	55	35	55
Spring Barley	82	40	49	52
Alfalfa	96	33	46	37
Protein peas	76	47	56	61
Rape-seed	91	47	49	60
Sugar beet	99	59	42	59

Table 8 Fitting criteria for yield supply and variable input allocation equations, CA+MEMC (two step)

	Acreage model	Yield model	Fertilizer model	Pesticides model
	Sim-R2 (%)	Sim-R2 (%)	Sim-R2 (%)	Sim-R2 (%)
Winter wheat	---	52	48	84
Corn	91	55	63	59
Spring Barley	82	38	75	85
Alfalfa	96	38	56	80
Protein peas	77	46	79	98
Rape-seed	91	47	74	91
Sugar beet	98	59	74	88

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